

The changing nature of human rights in the 21st century: challenges before India.

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Guide

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Abstract

Change is the universal law of nature. As a result of this change, the rules, laws, and ideas prevalent in society also undergo transformation. In the same way, various changes have been observed in the ideas related to human rights, which came into existence along with human civilization. In the early period, the form of human rights mainly focused on civil and natural rights. Later, at both the international and national levels, social, economic, and cultural human rights were accepted. At the same time, the concept of human rights, which was once individual-centered, has gradually moved toward group- and class-based concepts.

In the modern era, with the rapidly changing social, cultural, and economic conditions of the world, the concept of human rights continues to adopt new ideas and forms. The purpose of the present study is to highlight the progressive changes taking place in the concept of human rights and to analyse their usefulness.

Every being in society has the right to live. Therefore, it is also the duty of every being to ensure that their existence does not become an obstacle to another's life. In a general sense, this can be called the early form of modern human rights. This is the fundamental concept of human rights. The refined, advanced, and expanded concept of human rights that we see today includes within it the basic principle of "Live and let live."

Key Words: Human Rights, Human Rights Awareness, Challenges Before India, Changing Goals of Human Rights.

Introduction

Although the idea of human rights has existed since ancient times, only a few nations in the world formally recognized and accepted responsibility for

protecting them. During the Second World War, the Nazi regime in Germany brutally killed millions of innocent Jews. The cruel events revealed during the Nuremberg War Crimes Trials held between 1944 and 1946 made the entire world once again realize the urgent need for human rights.

In 1948, the Charter of the United Nations gave an important place to human rights. On 10 December 1948, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). The member nations signed this declaration, which stated that no government has any moral or legal right to say, "We can treat our citizens as we wish." From then onward, no government had the right to trample on the human rights of its citizens. If any government deprived its people of human rights, the international community could exert pressure on that government to restore those rights. In this sense, the declaration of human rights holds great importance.

There is a close and strong connection between the social, cultural, material, and spiritual progress of human beings. Though various external factors contribute to progress, the most important factor has always been the freedom available to human beings. The right to live according to one's will and to develop one's potential freely has enabled human advancement. The more freedom a person enjoys, the more courage and capacity he gains to move toward progress.

Human progress depends on the freedom available to individuals. When a person is free, he naturally feels inspired to grow and improve himself. This freedom creates a favourable environment for intellectual development and enhances human capability. When a society is enslaved or oppressed, it cannot progress; its growth is restricted. On the other hand, in a system where citizens enjoy maximum freedom, people contribute to the comprehensive development of themselves, their society, and their nation. Therefore, human rights are essential and valuable for both development and progress.

Human Rights

Human rights are the rights that nature itself has granted to every human being simply because they are human. Human dignity, equality between men and women, and individual freedom in the social context are all included within the scope of human rights. Based on the values of justice and equality, the noble idea that every person should have certain fundamental rights forms the essence of human rights.

The Greek philosopher Saint Thomas defined human rights as “those fundamental rights given to humans to make their life comfortable and meaningful.” Human rights arise from the principles of natural justice. These rights are not created by the force of any nation, law, or social agreement; rather, they exist inherently from the moment of a person’s birth.

The world-renowned thinker Prof. Harold Laski stated that “those rights without which an individual cannot achieve the full development of their personality are called human rights.” These are rights that no one can take away from any individual. They include the right to life, equality, freedom of thought and conscience, freedom of religion, right to education, nationality, freedom from exploitation, right to vote, right to participate in social and political activities, right to family protection, and the right to live without fear.

The origin of human rights can be traced through several important historical events:

- Magna Carta (1215), England
- Petition of Right (1618)
- Habeas Corpus Act (1676)
- Bill of Rights (1688)
- Declaration of Independence (1776), USA – announcing fundamental rights
- French Revolution (1789) – emphasizing liberty, equality, and fraternity
- Congress of Vienna (1815) – resolution against slavery
- Geneva and Hague Conventions – resolutions for the abolition of practices violating human dignity

In 1945, during World War II, the atomic bombings on Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan caused the death of over two lakh people and immense destruction of property. Such a large-scale loss of human life and resources had never occurred before in history. It was realized that if such destruction continued, humanity itself would cease to exist on Earth.

Therefore, to maintain international peace and security, and to promote economic and social development through global cooperation, as well as to protect human rights, the United Nations was established on 24 October 1945. Later, between January 1947 and December 1948, the Human Rights Commission drafted an international charter on human rights. On 10 December

1948, the United Nations General Assembly adopted the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), consisting of 30 articles. The member nations of the UN accepted the responsibility to protect and promote human rights worldwide.

Human Rights Awareness: The Challenges Before India

The medieval age was the era of duties, the modern age was about protection of rights, but sociologists around the world believe that the 21st century will be the age of brotherhood. The foundation of this belief lies in human rights awareness. The great Greek philosopher Saint Thomas Aquinas is regarded as the father of human rights.

In India, the lack of awareness about human rights has several causes—ignorance, population growth, and scarcity of resources. However, a major cause is also the lack of interest and concern for knowledge and development. To overcome this indifference, it is not only necessary but also essential to create awareness about human rights among people. The celebration of World Human Rights Day aims to spread this awareness among the masses and establish the rule of rights through public participation.

The United Nations adopted the Universal Declaration of Human Rights on 10 December 1948, and since then, the day has been observed globally as World Human Rights Awareness Day to commemorate this event.

In India, although political transformation has been significant, even after celebrating the Golden Jubilee of Independence, India still remains a developing nation, not a developed one. The key reason behind this is the lack of awareness about rights. A country where human rights do not progress cannot expect meaningful human development.

India lags about fifty years behind the world in implementing human rights, and in terms of mindset, perhaps thousands of miles away. Despite repeated appeals from the Central Government, even progressive states like Maharashtra have been delaying the establishment of State Human Rights Commissions. The Srikrishna Commission Report, which clearly documented violations of human rights, was set aside and ignored—this is a harsh reality.

If we truly want to prevent such occurrences in the future, it is crucial that citizens gain knowledge and awareness about human rights and actively work to protect them.

Human Rights Awareness and the Need for Social Awakening

Conscious and deliberate efforts must be made to create public awareness and build a social awakening toward human rights. Only then can the 21st century truly become a century of brotherhood.

The greatest violation of human rights can be traced to the imperialist mindset that created slavery. Today, the United States of America stands as a dominant superpower. However, the same America—whose leaders speak about universal human rights—has often been accused of mass killings and violating the very principles it claims to uphold. Former U.S. President Bill Clinton, despite his advocacy for global human rights, has been criticized for actions that contradicted these ideals. The global politics of disarming developing nations through economic power is a clear example of human rights suppression. To escape such domination, every nation must understand and protect its own rights.

The United Nations, in 1948, adopted the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which India has officially accepted. Accordingly, India enacted the Protection of Human Rights Act, ensuring that violations of these rights could be addressed through proper legal mechanisms. To enforce this, the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) was established with judicial powers to inquire into violations and punish those responsible. The central government has also urged every state to form State Human Rights Commissions.

The NHRC has appointed representatives in every district, and citizens can directly contact them in case of any human rights violations. Despite such systems being in place, it is not acceptable for the public to remain indifferent or unaware. Schools, colleges, universities, and various organizations must take responsibility to educate every citizen about their rights.

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, every person is born free and is entitled to equal rights without any form of discrimination. Each human being has the right to life and protection. No person should ever be enslaved or forced into bonded labour. No one has the right to torture, insult, or discriminate against another. Behind all these provisions lies the belief that every person should live with dignity and respect.

Human rights ensure equality before the law, and every constitution emphasizes the establishment and enforcement of fundamental rights. Everyone has the freedom to seek justice if their rights are violated. Every individual is presumed

innocent until proven guilty, and has the right to be treated as such. The right to privacy is one of the most important human rights, ensuring that everyone can live a personal life free from intrusion.

Every person also has the right to citizenship, freedom of movement, and asylum. These rights have allowed individuals like Andrei Sakharov, Aleksandr Solzhenitsyn, Salman Rushdie, Taslima Nasreen, and Benazir Bhutto to survive persecution.

Furthermore, everyone has the right to housing, employment, parenthood, marriage, education, healthcare, and basic welfare facilities so that life becomes more comfortable and dignified. Property, livelihood, or employment—the essential means of living—cannot be taken away unlawfully. If such rights are violated, every ordinary citizen has the right to seek justice.

Protection and Awareness of Human Rights in India

Every individual has the right to seek justice. If a person is poor, they have the right to free legal aid (lawyer) to help them fight for justice. Every person also has the right to livelihood and to receive equal pay for equal work. Furthermore, every citizen has the right to opportunities and facilities that help them overcome weakness, disability, neglect, or incapacity. The rights to motherhood protection, child security, and care are also part of human rights.

Human rights also include cultural protection, the freedom to enjoy art, and even the equal right of all people to benefit from scientific progress. The world is gradually becoming more generous in recognizing these universal rights. If we, in such a time, remain unaware of even the basic understanding of these rights, future generations will not forgive us. Hence, it is essential to build awareness about human rights among all.

As society develops, the scope of these rights continues to expand. In recent years, the Right to Information (RTI) has gained strong recognition. Additionally, Public Interest Litigations (PILs) are being filed in large numbers to challenge violations and restrictions on rights. However, due to lack of knowledge about the law, legal process, and justice system, people often rush to the Supreme Court unnecessarily. Many do not know that even an ordinary citizen can file a PIL in their local court.

Even writing a simple petition on a postcard asking for protection against injustice can be an effective tool for defending one's rights. Many judges, police officers, and district officials take such human rights violations seriously,

showing signs of administrative sensitivity and responsibility. Although “darkness has spread,” there is still light of hope.

In India, several PILs have been filed demanding clean water and air, leading to significant environmental reforms, including mandatory production of eco-friendly vehicles. These were all victories in the fight for human rights.

During the coalition government in Maharashtra, several police encounters occurred where criminals were killed without the police being harmed. When families of the deceased demanded justice, it became difficult for the police to respond—highlighting serious concerns of human rights violations.

India is a free and democratic republic, meaning every citizen is independent and has equal rights. However, delays in delivering justice are now considered violations of human rights. How can a country be called “developed” if a case filed by a grandfather is only resolved in his grandson’s lifetime?

Currently, the system for protecting and implementing human rights in India functions with limited resources. Therefore, it is essential to increase efficiency and speed in these mechanisms. The National Human Rights Commission must be strengthened with adequate manpower, expert officials, and a nationwide network.

As the next year marks the Golden Jubilee of the Republic of India, every state and union territory should urgently establish a State Human Rights Commission. District representatives must receive training, communication facilities, and office infrastructure, as many currently spend from their own pockets for travel, postage, and other expenses. The protection and promotion of human rights should not depend on individual capacity or sacrifice.

The permanence of rights is the essence of human rights philosophy. Equality is inherent in the protection of these rights. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, in his final speech to the Constituent Assembly on 25 November 1949, asked a vital question:

“How long shall we continue to deny equality in our social and economic life? If we do not achieve it soon, our political democracy itself will be in danger.”

The same applies to the neglect of human rights. Therefore, it is our duty to awaken public consciousness and build mass awareness about human rights throughout the nation.

Changing Goals of Human Rights in the 21st Century

Human rights are the basic and natural rights of every human being, given without any discrimination of caste, religion, race, language, gender, region, or political belief. The concept developed from natural justice, which states that every person is born with certain inherent rights.

The idea of human rights was first seen in the Greek and Roman Empires. Its early form appeared in England's Magna Carta (1215). Later, the Petition of Rights (1628), the Bill of Rights (1689), and the American Declaration of Independence (1776) strengthened this concept.

After the Second World War, the need to protect human dignity became global. The United Nations (UNO) was formed, and on 10 December 1948, it adopted the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). Since then, 10 December is celebrated worldwide as Human Rights Day.

The UDHR gives everyone the right to life, liberty, equality, and security. It bans slavery, injustice, and cruelty and ensures freedom, justice, and dignity for all. It also guarantees freedom of speech, religion, movement, and association, as well as rights to education, work, health, rest, and social security.

No authority has the power to take away human rights, as they belong equally to all. That is why human rights have gained recognition and acceptance across the world.

In India, the Protection of Human Rights Act (1993) was passed, and the National and State Human Rights Commissions were established to protect and promote these rights, ensuring justice and equality for every citizen in the 21st century.

Establishment and Future Challenges of Human Rights Commissions

Human Rights Commissions have been established in India, including the State Commission in Maharashtra. However, even after 76 years of the global human rights movement, violations continue to occur worldwide. The main reason is the lack of human rights education among the general public, due to which human rights literacy has not taken deep root in society.

Although some awareness exists, the commissions often lack adequate systems, staff, and resources to meet public expectations. The government's support is limited, as authorities sometimes feel that the commissions act against political interests, which reflects ignorance about their true purpose.

Over the last seven decades, special rights have been recognized globally for the disabled, mentally challenged, elderly, women, and children, emphasizing that every marginalized group must live with dignity and respect. When the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was published in 1948, it accepted the principle that human dignity depends on equality, unity, freedom, justice, and peace.

In the future, greater emphasis will be placed on preventive measures to stop human rights violations. Due to the rising abuse of foreign citizens and maltreatment of migrants, there are discussions about establishing an International Court for Human Rights, similar to the International Court of Justice at The Hague.

Because of globalization, migration has increased rapidly, creating new cultural and social challenges. Wars, natural disasters, and political instability in countries like Afghanistan, Libya, Syria, Iraq, Ukraine, and Russia have forced millions to migrate, leading to statelessness, which has become a serious global issue.

Growing inequality has created severe health crises in underdeveloped countries, especially in Asia and Africa. Even developed nations face threats to social security systems due to rising bankruptcies. Economists and sociologists fear that this may soon endanger the health and living standards of common people.

Climate change is also destabilizing nature, causing tsunamis, global warming, soil erosion, and natural disasters, as seen in recent storms in Japan and the USA and floods in Thailand.

In the future, efforts will focus on ensuring that every human being, regardless of caste, religion, gender, custom, or economic status, is seen and treated simply as a human being—so that human life becomes more dignified and respectful across the world.

Towards an Equal and Just Human Society

In the future, the focus will be on building a non-discriminatory and equal human society. People will be valued not by their traditional status or position but by the simple and just principle of being human by birth.

Today, the problems of migrant workers, the elderly, tribal communities, and fishermen are becoming increasingly serious. These marginalized groups are being deprived of basic human rights, and addressing their protection has become one of the major challenges of the 21st century.

In India, being a democratic country with an active media and aware citizens, the judiciary holds great importance, and so does the protection of human rights. Yet, violations and negligence continue to occur frequently. Riots, protests, violent clashes, and the frequent use of armed police and military forces all lead to the reduction of human rights.

Government negligence in areas like police reforms, healthcare, education quality, and food security has caused widespread suffering and daily violations of human rights. Due to globalization and economic reforms, the rich are becoming richer, increasing inequality — a clear sign of human rights erosion.

In regions like Kashmir, Manipur, and Nagaland, military control has resulted in the restriction of civil rights. Maoist and Naxalite attacks have also made large sections of people in rural, forest, and hilly areas victims of human rights violations. Terrorist bomb blasts have created fear and instability in cities, while crimes against women continue to rise, marking another grave concern. The neglect of poor and orphaned children in terms of education, healthcare, and rehabilitation reflects the government's serious failure in human rights protection.

The happiness and prosperity of any society do not depend only on material wealth, but on how safe and secure daily life is. In this regard, there is a wide gap between India and many smaller nations like Singapore, Malaysia, and Hong Kong, where essential facilities such as clean water, electricity, roads, health, and communication have become part of everyday life and essential human rights.

In India, the poor condition of roads, polluted water, and increasing health problems directly violate basic human needs and rights. It is surprising that leaders and authorities fail to recognize this. Lack of communication between the government and citizens is a threat to democracy and shows clear neglect of human rights — something that urgently needs attention and change.

Conclusion

Equality is an essential part of protecting human rights. On 25 November 1949, during his final speech to the Constituent Assembly, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar asked a vital question:

“How long shall we continue to deny equality in our social and economic life? If we do not achieve it soon, our political democracy itself will be in danger.”

The same is true for the neglect of human rights. Therefore, it is necessary to spread public awareness about them. To make 21st-century India progressive, human rights education must be given special importance.

A strong and effective system is needed to protect and implement these rights. The Human Rights Act of 1993 mainly focuses on structure but does not clearly state:

What human rights are,

How awareness will be spread,

What action will be taken after violations, and

How a common person can seek justice at every level.

Such laws lose meaning when governments avoid accountability. Even after many years of democracy, lack of awareness about human rights in India shows weak civic understanding.

Hence, civil society should take the lead. By promoting education, awareness programs, and including human rights in school curricula, we can create responsible and informed citizens. Only then can India achieve a just, equal, and dignified society in the 21st century.

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